

APPLICATION OF SCHOOL MAPPING PRINCIPLES IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF NON-FORMAL AND ADULT EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN NORTH-WEST NIGERIA

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Abstract

Nigeria faces persistent challenges in providing inclusive education, with over 10 million out-of-school children and millions of illiterate adults, particularly in the northern region. This study examines the application of school mapping principles, including demographic, geographic, and economic factors, in the planning and establishment of non-formal and adult education institutions in the North-West Zone of Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Using a descriptive survey approach, data were collected from State Agencies for Mass Literacy and Non-Formal Education and Non-Governmental Organizations across three states. Findings reveal that while demographic and geographic principles are partially applied, equity and socio-cultural principles are inadequately integrated, leading to the persistent exclusion of marginalized groups, particularly women and rural dwellers. The study concluded that strategic school mapping is indispensable for effective non-formal education planning in North West Nigeria and recommends strengthening data-driven planning, community engagement, and integration of life skills into literacy programs.

Keywords: School mapping principles, non-formal education, adult education, mass literacy

Introduction

Education is central to Nigeria's human development strategy, yet access remains inequitable. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), in her National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014), "education is an instrument 'par excellence' which equips an individual with the right skills, knowledge, abilities, competence, attitudes, behaviour and values to function effectively in the society." Education in its broadest sense is any act or experience that has a formative effect on the mind, character, or physical ability of an individual. Education encompasses all life experiences that help individuals cultivate skills, values, and behaviours that contribute positively to the society they belong to (Fafunwa, in Udosen, 2016, p. 3). Despite policy commitments through the Universal Basic Education Act, the Education for All goals, and Sustainable Development Goal 4, millions of people remain outside the formal school system. Non-formal education has therefore become a crucial alternative for addressing illiteracy and equipping marginalised populations with functional skills. However, planning for non-formal education has been inconsistent, often overlooking local demographic, geographic, and socio-cultural realities. This study investigates the application of school mapping principles as a planning tool for establishing non-formal and adult education centres in North-West Nigeria.

School mapping, originating from France in the 1960s, is a micro-planning tool that utilises demographic and spatial data to inform the distribution of educational facilities (Calloids, 2011; John and Ogonziek, 2018; NIEPA, 1997). In developing countries, it is critical to address inequities in access, particularly for disadvantaged groups (UNESCO, 2015). Nigerian literature

emphasises the persistent challenges of illiteracy, with over 62 million adults unable to read or write (National Commission for Mass Literacy and Non-Formal Education, NMEC, 2017).

Demographic analysis is central to school mapping because educational planning is inherently tied to a target population that is continually changing in size, age, sex composition, and spatial distribution (UNICEF, 2017). Planning without demographic consideration risks misallocating resources and failing to meet the educational needs of communities. Eloundou-Enyegue, Giroux, and Tenikue (2021) distinguish between static demographic analysis, which examines the current composition and structure of a population, and dynamic demographic analysis, which explores trends and movements shaped by births, deaths, and migration. Both are essential for anticipating demand, forecasting enrolments, and identifying underserved groups. Effective school mapping therefore requires integration of demographic variables with social, economic, and geographic data to inform decisions on location, access, and resource allocation. The absence of demographic considerations in educational planning has historically weakened initiatives. For instance, in India, numerous commissions and policies—ranging from the expansion of compulsory education to school feeding programmes—have been designed without sufficient consideration of population distribution, resulting in uneven access and inefficiencies (UNICEF, 2017). This demonstrates that demographic grounding is not only necessary for formal schooling but also critical for non-formal and adult education centres, where learners are often concentrated in marginalised, migratory, or underserved populations. Hence, applying demographic principles in the establishment of such centres allows planners to identify areas of most tremendous demand, align programmes with the age and occupational structure of target learners, and adapt to changing population dynamics. Ultimately, demographic analysis ensures that school mapping goes beyond a universal design towards context-sensitive planning, balancing efficiency, equity, and cost-effectiveness while striving to provide inclusive education opportunities for all.

The application of geographic principles of school mapping to the establishment of non-formal and adult education institutions in Nigeria is central to strengthening educational systems for national development. Planning for non-formal and adult education has often been constrained by inadequate facilities and the absence of systematic spatial analysis, leading to institutions being established without regard to geographic realities (Norris, 2017). As a result, non-formal education has frequently been overlooked, despite its critical role in extending learning opportunities to adults and marginalised populations. Geographic principles emphasise the spatial distribution of educational facilities and their relationship to population needs, settlement patterns, and administrative structures. By situating educational institutions within their geographic context—whether rural or urban, regional or national—planners can ensure more equitable access and effective resource allocation (Norris, 2017). This approach recognises that the characteristics of its locality shape education, and thus vary across districts depending on demographic, social, and economic factors. Oleshko and Petrovska (2020) argue that spatial variations inevitably influence requirements for educational provision, mirroring other social phenomena that have long been studied through geographic analysis. For NAEIs, adopting this principle enables planners to systematically assess where, when, and how to establish institutions in ways that respond to the diverse needs of learners, particularly in underserved and hard-to-reach communities. Ultimately, applying geographic principles in school mapping allows non-formal and adult education to move beyond fragmented provision. It ensures that institutions are strategically located, responsive to community needs, and integrated into broader educational development, thereby enhancing both efficiency and inclusivity.

Economics, as the study of scarcity and choice, directly informs educational planning by guiding the allocation of limited resources among competing needs (Martins, 2009). Education planners must decide what type of education to provide, how to provide it, and for whom, given financial constraints (Bradley, 2019). Human capital theory underscores the role of education in productivity, innovation, and national development (Akinyemi, 2013; Famurewa, 2014). Yet, in Nigeria, the colonial legacy left an education system oriented toward clerical work rather than industrial or technical development, contributing to persistent youth unemployment (Oyebamiji, 2006). Non-formal education, by contrast, offers opportunities to reskill and upskill adults, filling gaps left by the formal system. Nwadiani (2000) identifies key economic dimensions of educational planning, including resource generation, allocation, and utilisation; educational finance; taxation; and costing. Applying these principles to the establishment of non-formal and adult education institutions ensures that limited resources are distributed efficiently, with a focus on demand and supply, regional equity, and long-term sustainability. Successful global examples, such as Kenya's village polytechnics and Botswana's Brigades, illustrate how employment-oriented non-formal programmes can strengthen human capital development (Ngwu, 2003). However, in Nigeria, underfunding and poor programme design continue to hinder progress (Alani & Isola, 2009; Oyebamiji, 2008). Taken together, the demographic, geographic, and economic principles of school mapping provide a comprehensive framework for planning non-formal and adult education. Demography identifies who needs education, geography determines where institutions should be located, and economics addresses how resources are mobilised and allocated. Integrating these principles into planning ensures that non-formal and adult education institutions are not only responsive to learner needs but also sustainable and equitable. For Nigeria, applying these principles offers a pathway to strengthen human capital development and reduce educational exclusion.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. How is the demographic principle of school mapping applied to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in the North West Zone, Nigeria?
2. In what way is the geographic principle of school mapping applied to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in the North West Zone, Nigeria?
3. To what extent is the economic principle of school mapping applied to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in the North West Zone, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

- H0₁**: There is no significant difference in the opinion of staff of State Agencies for Non-Formal Education, NGOs and Field Workers on the application of the demographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions In North West Zone, Nigeria;
- H0₂**: There is no significant difference in the opinion of staff of State Agencies for Non-Formal Education, NGOs and Field Workers on the application of geographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria; and
- H0₃**: There is no significant difference in the opinion of staff of State Agencies for Non-Formal Education, NGOs and Field Workers on the application of the economic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria.

Methods

This study adopted a survey research design. Respondents included executive directors, department heads, and field staff from state agencies for Mass Literacy and NGOs across Kaduna, Kano, Jigawa, Katsina, Sokoto, Zamfara, and Kebbi states. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and interviews, focusing on the extent to which the three school mapping principles were applied. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze responses, while qualitative insights were coded thematically.

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the opinions of the staff of state Agencies and Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs) staff on the application of the demographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria. Items 21-30 in the questionnaire relate to this Hypothesis. Responses of all respondents were collected, analyzed and presented in a table using an Independent sample (t-test). Thus, Table 1 gives the details.

Table 1:Independent Sample t-test of Staff of State Agencies and NGOs on the Application of Demographic Principle of School Mapping to the Establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	Df	SD	t.cal	t.cri	p-value	Decision
Staff of State Agencies	90	4.790	177	0.234	0.32	1.08	0.59	H0 ₃ Retained
NGOs	90	3.520	2	1.796				
Total	180	8.310						

As revealed on table 1, it was evident that mean of 4.790 and standard deviation of 0.234 for staff of state Agencies while Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) staff have the mean of 3.520 with standard deviation of 1.796. The t.cal 0.32 is less than t.cri 1.08 and the p-value is 0.59 (P>0.05). The null-hypothesis (H0₃) is thus, retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the staff of state Agencies and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) staff on the application of demographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education In. This finding suggests a shared perspective among both State Agency and NGO staff on the relevance and application of demographic principles in planning educational interventions. Despite the differences in institutional mandates, funding structures, and operational approaches, both groups appear to recognise the importance of demographic data—such as population density, age distribution, and geographic accessibility—in determining the location and viability of Non-Formal and Adult Education centres. Follow-up interviews with respondents revealed that the non-formal education agencies of the government relied mainly on technical support, such as training and financial support from NGOs, to run their organisations. Another possible explanation for this convergence in opinion is the increasing emphasis on data-driven planning in Nigeria’s education, resulting from the influence of international organisations such as PLANE, TARL, and UNICEF. Both governmental and non-governmental actors are increasingly exposed to national policy frameworks and global best practices that prioritise equitable access to education, especially in underserved regions. The alignment in views may also reflect collaborative

efforts between these stakeholders in implementing educational programs, particularly in rural and marginalised communities where demographic considerations are critical.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the opinions of the staff of state Agencies and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) staff on the application of the geographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria. Items 31-40 in the questionnaire relate to this Hypothesis. Responses of all respondents were collected, analysed and presented in a table using an Independent sample (t-test). Thus, Table 2 gives the details.

Table 2: Independent Sample t-test of Staff of State Agencies and NGOs on the Application of Geographic Principle of School Mapping to the Establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	df	SD	p-value	t.cal	t.cri	Decision
Staff of State Agencies	90	1.251	177	3.306	0.61	0.189	1.281	H0 ₄ Retained
NGOs	90	2.416	2	1.261				
Total	180	3.667						

As revealed on table 2, it was evident that mean of 1.251 and standard deviation of 3.306 for Staff of State Agencies while Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) staff have the mean of 2.416 with standard deviation of 1.261. While the t.cal 0.189 is less than t.cri 1.281. The p-value is 0.61 ($P > 0.05$). The null-hypothesis (H0₄) is thus, retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between Staff of State Agencies while Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) staff with regards to application of geographic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria. This outcome suggests a shared understanding and alignment between State Agency and NGO staff regarding the importance of geographic factors such as terrain, proximity to population centers, transportation networks, and environmental accessibility in determining the placement of educational institutions. Despite their differing organisational structures and operational scopes, both groups appear to value geographic data as a critical component in ensuring equitable access to education, particularly in underserved and remote areas. Interestingly, while the mean scores differ (1.251 for State Agencies and 2.416 for NGOs), the lack of statistical significance implies that these differences are not strong enough to reflect a meaningful divergence in opinion. The relatively high standard deviation among State Agency staff (SD = 3.306) compared to NGO staff (SD = 1.261) may indicate greater variability in responses within the government sector. This could be attributed to differences in regional responsibilities, resource availability, or exposure to geographic planning tools such as GIS and Google Earth among various state departments.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the opinions of the staff of state Agencies and Non-Governmental organisations (NGOs) staff on the application of the economic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria. Items 41-50 in the questionnaire relate to this Hypothesis. Responses of all respondents were collected, analysed and presented in a table using an Independent sample (t-test). Thus, Table 3 gives the details.

Table 3: Independent Sample t-test of Staff of State Agencies and NGOs on the Application of Economic Principle of School Mapping to the Establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in North West Zone, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	df	SD	p-value	t.cal	t.cri	Decision
Staff of State Agencies	90	0.215	177	2.501	0.82	2.471	4.194	H0 ₅ Retained
NGOs	90	6.174	2	0.768				
Total	180	6.389						

As revealed in table 3, it was evident that mean of 0.215 and the standard deviation of 2.501 for the Staff of State Agencies, while the Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) staff have a mean of 6.174 with a standard deviation of 0.768. While the t.cal 0.82 is less than t.cri 4.194. The p-value is 0.82 ($P > 0.05$). The null-hypothesis (H_0) is thus retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the Staff of State Agencies and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) concerning the application of the economic principle of school mapping to the establishment of Non-Formal and Adult Education Institutions in the North West Zone, Nigeria. While the quantitative data suggest convergence in practice, further interviews provided more profound insight into how these similarities are experienced and rationalised by practitioners.

Thematic Analysis and Discussion Interviews with staff from state agencies highlighted structural and bureaucratic factors that shape their engagement with school mapping. Respondents explained that although they are aware of the economic principles underpinning school mapping, their application is often constrained by rigid government budgeting cycles, political directives, and resource limitations. One state official remarked: *“We know the importance of locating schools based on population distribution and cost-efficiency, but often the final decisions are influenced by political considerations, such as where influential leaders want projects to be sited.”* By contrast, interviews with NGO staff revealed that while they also utilise school mapping principles, their approaches are often more flexible and community-driven. Several NGO workers described using rapid community assessments, GIS mapping, and participatory rural appraisals to complement formal economic criteria. An NGO respondent noted: *“We have to ensure that communities feel ownership. Sometimes the purely economic model does not capture cultural or social realities, so we balance cost-effectiveness with inclusivity.”*

Interestingly, both groups acknowledged that while their methods might differ in process, the outcome often converges, leading to the absence of a significant statistical difference found in the survey. However, the interviews suggest that the pathways to applying school mapping principles diverge: State Agencies rely more on formal policy frameworks, while NGOs employ adaptive, grassroots-oriented strategies. A recurrent theme across both groups was the challenge of equity versus efficiency. While the economic principle prioritizes optimal allocation of limited resources, many respondents emphasized the need to reach marginalized populations in remote or conflict-affected communities, even when this was not the most cost-efficient option. This tension reflects broader debates in educational planning in Nigeria, where equity, political realities, and community needs intersect with economic rationality. Results indicate uneven application of school mapping principles: Demographic: Population projections are inconsistently applied, leading to misallocation of resources. Geographic: Distance and accessibility issues persist, with many centres located far from marginalized communities. Economic: Cost-effectiveness is considered, but opportunity costs for learners (especially youth engaged in labour) are neglected. The findings

highlight that without deliberate application of all principles, non-formal education centres risk perpetuating inequities rather than reducing them.

Conclusion

Non-formal and adult education remains Nigeria's best opportunity to reduce illiteracy and equip marginalised populations with functional skills. School mapping provides a viable planning tool, but is currently underutilised in the North-West Zone. To ensure inclusivity and sustainability, policymakers must integrate community-driven planning, address socio-cultural barriers, and strengthen the data infrastructure for micro-level educational planning.

Recommendations

1. Adopt comprehensive school mapping frameworks that integrate demographic, geographic, and socio-cultural data by supporting development of homegrown tools and processes such as offline maps, apps in local languages and by people from the communities
2. Strengthen NMEC and SAMES capacity for evidence-based planning and monitoring. Build capacity for using digital mapping tools like google earth and Maps and possible local development of data collection models
3. Enhance community participation to align programs with local realities.
4. Promote equity-focused interventions, particularly for women, nomadic groups, and rural dwellers.

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